

ISSN 0974-0775

NAAS Rating : 4.79

GREEN FARMING

(International Journal of Applied Agricultural & Horticultural Sciences)

(Abbreviation : *Green Farming Int. J.*)

Volume 6

Number 4

July-August 2015

Bimonthly

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Effect of growth hormones on the seed production CMS lines in rice

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Received : 01 November 2014 ; Revised accepted : 16 June 2015

ABSTRACT

Comparative effects of four treatments 60 ppm GA₃, 40 ppm GA₃, 60 ppm Mangiferin and 40 ppm Mangiferin along with control were tested on seed production aspects of four cyto-sterile line viz., IR 58025A, PMS 2A, PMS 3A and PMS 10A. It was observed that all the treatments scored much higher values than control for the characters like duration of florets opening, angle of florets opening, exerted stigma, panicle exertion, grain yield per ha etc. Cyto-sterile line PMS 10A, PMS 3A and PMS 2A possessed better important floral traits than IR 58025A. However, cyto-sterile line IR 58025A scored much higher values for seed grain yield per ha, spikelet length and plant height.

Key words : CMS lines, Cyto-sterile line, GA₃, Hybrid seed production, Mangiferin, Rice, Yield parameters.

INTRODUCTION

Low out crossing of CMS lines in rice is one of the major problems for low seed set in hybrid seed production plots. A cyto-sterile line with high out crossing potential will economize the cost of hybrid seed production. Male sterility is most important trait to influence out crossing. Male fertile plant show very little, if any out crossing due to self pollinating nature of rice flower. However in male sterile plants, extent of out crossing is further influenced by its floral trait. The genetic variability for floral traits such as angle of florets, duration of florets openings, exerted stigma and panicle exertion exist in rice (Singh, 2012). Growth hormones like GA₃ are known to expression influence floral traits and out crossing. Some studies have indicated Mangiferin as cheaper alternative of GA₃ (Singh and Shao, 1997 & 1998). The aim of present experiment was to establish the effectiveness of Mangiferin as new growth hormone and cheaper alternative of GA₃ by testing its performance over number of cyto-sterile lines.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment comprised of five treatments (Table 1) including control. The treatments were selected based on previous studies (Singh & Sahoo, 1997 & 1998). These five treatments were tested on four cyto-sterile lines viz., IR 58025A, PMS 2A, PMS 3A and PMS 10A (Table 2). Cyto-sterile line IR 58025A/B, PMS 2A/B and PMS 10A/B were planted into 4:2 ratios. A spacing of 20 cm was maintained between lines and 15 cm with in lines. Each plot consisted of two set of A: B in 4:2 ratio of two meter row length. The experiment was laid out in RB Design with three replications during *khari* (summer) of

Table 1. Different selected treatments used to study comparative response of four cyto-sterile lines in rice

Treatment No.	Treatments
T ₁	60 ppm GA ₃
T ₂	60 ppm Mangiferin
T ₃	40 ppm GA ₃
T ₄	40 ppm Mangiferin
T ₅	Control

2010 and 2011 at Experimental Farm of Instt. of Agric. Sciences, BHU, Varanasi. Solutions of different treatments were prepared as follows:

(a) GA₃ solution : GA₃ was prepared in two different concentrations. For preparing 40 ppm GA₃ solution, 40 mg of GA₃ powder was mixed with 40 ml of ethyl alcohol to dissolve, and then water was added to make the volume up to 1 liter. The resulting solution was having 40 ppm of GA₃ concentration. Same procedure was followed to prepare 60 ppm of GA₃ solution.

(b) Mangifer in solution : Mangiferin a new growth hormone is extracted from malformed mango plant parts. Mangiferin is soluble in water, when it is mixed with Glycine in 1:1 ratio. For preparing 40 ppm mangiferin solution, 40 mg of mangiferin was mixed with 40 mg of Glycine and this mixture was dissolved. Similarly 60 ppm concentration of mangiferin was also prepared.

(c) Flag leaf clipping: At five per cent flowering stage, the flag leaves were clipped with the help of scissor. This may enhance the out crossing by allowing free flow of pollen of the B to A.

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Table 2. Cyto-sterile lines used for hybrid seed production studies

Sr. No.	Cyto-sterile line	Feature characteristics
1	IR 58025A	Plants are of medium in height (75 cm with long size panicle and high exertion percentage (60%), spikelet's are open for more than 2.5 hours with wide angle of florets opening and high percent of stigma exertion with long slender grains.
2	PMS 2A	Plants are of medium height (76 cm) bearing long size panicles, high panicle exertion percentage (70%), spikelets remain open for more than two hour with wide angle of opening of florets and high percentage of stigma exertion.
3	PMS 3A	Plants are of medium stature (78 cm) bearing long size panicle and spikelet's, panicle exertion is about sixty five per cent, the florets remain open for more than two and half hour. With high degree of angle and high per cent of stigma exertion.
4	PMS 10A	Plants are of medium in height (75 cm) with long panicles, panicle exertion is about sixty eight per cent, florets remain opened for more than two and high percent of stigma exertion.

(d) Rope pulling: Rope pulling was performed to increase the supplementary pollination in the absence of high wind velocity.

The treatments were applied with low volume sprayer at 5 percent of flowering stage. The observations on following characters were recorded i) Duration of opening of florets (min), ii) Exserted stigma percentage, iii) Angle of florets opening, iv) Length of spikelet's, v) Plant height, vi) Panicle exertion percentage and, vii) grain yield per hectare. The data recorded on the different treatments were subjected to statistical analysis based on simple means of the various characters of five plants under observation in three replications. Analysis of variance was performed following Panse and Sukhatue (1954).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Comparative effect of 4 treatments *viz.*, 60 ppm and 40 ppm, GA₃; 60 ppm and 40 ppm, Mangiferin along with control were observed on four cyto-sterile lines *viz.*, IR 58025A, PMS 2A, PMS 3A and PMS 10A. The data on eight characters which may influence out crossing were evaluated on the basis of mean performance of all the four cyto-sterile lines. In general on the mean performance basis it was observed that all the treatments scored much higher values than control for the characters like duration of florets opening, angle of opened florets, panicle exertion, spikelet length and grain yield per ha. Keeping these performances in view the treatments for their effectiveness were ranked as 1) GA₃ 60 ppm, 2) Mangiferin 60 ppm, 3) GA₃ 40 ppm, 4) Mangiferin 40 ppm 5) and control (Table 3).

Exception to this ranking was grain yield per ha where GA₃ 40 ppm was ranked 5th because it scored less values than control (ranked 4th). One of the interesting observations was

that GA₃ affected more to plant height than mangiferin similar observation were made by Singh and Sahoo (1997 & 1998). Spikelet length was not much affected by application of different treatments only exception was 60 ppm GA₃. It was clearly established by this experiment that mangiferin as well as GA₃ have positive effect on experiment floral and related traits and also they helped in better seed setting on all the four cyto-sterile lines. Singh & Sahoo (1997) reported similar findings on single cyto-sterile lines IR 58025A. Comparative response of different cyto-sterile lines were evaluated on the basis of mean effect of five treatments, which indicated that cyto-sterile lines PMS-10A, PMS-3A and PMS-2A performed better for important floral traits like duration of opening of florets, angle of opened florets, percentage of exserted stigma and panicle exertion than IR-58025A (Table 3). However, cyto-sterile line IR-58025A scored much higher values for grain yield per ha, spikelet length and plant height. Similar trends were observed when control data were evaluated, indicating equal response to all the four cyto-sterile lines. For grain yield per ha (mean over five treatments) IR-58025A/B (2499 kg) recorded much higher values than PMS-10A (157 kg), PMS-3A (239 kg) and PMS-2A (191 kg) (Table 3). Similar trends were observed when control data were compared for the four cyto-sterile lines indicating pronounced out crossing potential in cyto-sterile line IR 58025A. Virmani (1994) and Singh (2012) have also reported high about out crossing potential of IR 58025A in Indian conditions. On the basis of present investigation it can be concluded that (a) Glycine does help in influencing the seed yield and important floral traits of cyto-sterile lines; (b) New growth hormone mangiferin has established its positive impact on seed production of cyto-sterile lines. More comparative studies particularly on economics of mangiferin vs GA₃ are required before it is recommended as substitute of GA₃; (c) All the four cyto-sterile lines responded equally well to the use of out crossing promoters on floral attributes and seed setting percentage and (d) In case of IR 58025 A/B seed setting was much higher than PMS 10 A, PMS 3 A and PMS 2A indicating that there is something more than mere floral characteristics, which influence out crossing of CMS lines in rice. Similar trends have been observed by Singh (2009, 2012 and 2014) and Singh and Lekha Ram (2012) on different set of CMS lines as well as different set of treatments. More such studies with different set of male sterile lines in rice with new set of cheaper hormones needs to be conducted to economize the cost of hybrid rice seed production & ultimately cost of per unit of Hybrid Rice.

REFERENCES

- Pansae V G and Sukhatme P V. 1954. *Statistical Methods For Agricultural Workers*- 2nd Edn. ICAR, New Delhi. pp 381.
- Singh Rajesh. 2009. *Hybrid Rice Seed Production*. MM Technical Bulletin No 2. pp. 48.
- Singh Rajesh. 2012. *Hybrid Rice and Maize Seed Production*. MM Technical Bulletin. No 4. pp. 44

Table 3. Effect of different growth hormones on different characters in four cyto-sterile lines in rice

Sr. No.	Treatments	IR58025A	PMS 2A	PMS 3A	PMS 10A	Mean CMS	Over
I. Duration of opening of florets							
1	GA ₃ 60 ppm	95.67	160.33	192.81	169.90	154.63	
2	Mangiferin ppm	60	90.33	149.33	172.39	161.83	143.47
3	GA ₃ 40 ppm		76.00	158.67	172.35	163.47	142.62
4	Mangiferin ppm	40	121.67	152.67	137.80	157.00	142.28
5	Control		90.00	121.00	121.95	152.50	121.36
	Mean over treatments		94.74	148.90	159.46	160.80	
II. Angle of opened florets							
1	GA ₃ 60 ppm	25.00	32.67	31.67	31.50	30.21	
2	Mangiferin ppm	60	24.33	25.80	32.00	31.17	28.32
3	GA ₃ 40 ppm		30.00	27.57	23.53	31.03	28.03
4	Mangiferin ppm	40	25.00	29.44	27.23	30.33	28.00
5	Control		25.00	27.67	23.33	30.33	26.58
	Mean over treatments		25.86	28.67	27.33	30.87	
III. Percentage of exerted stigma							
1	GA ₃ 60 ppm	95.00	95.00	92.77	93.67	94.11	
2	Mangiferin ppm	60	95.00	94.43	93.33	92.33	93.77
3	GA ₃ 40 ppm		89.33	94.00	94.00	89.33	91.67
4	Mangiferin ppm	40	95.00	96.00	93.33	92.33	94.17
5	Control		76.67	96.00	94.67	92.67	90.01
	Mean over treatments		90.20	95.08	93.62	92.67	
IV. Spikelet length							
1	GA ₃ 60 ppm	10.96	9.11	10.20	9.71	9.99	
2	Mangiferin ppm	60	10.62	9.26	9.32	8.39	9.39
3	GA ₃ 40 ppm		10.39	9.42	9.40	9.36	9.64
4	Mangiferin ppm	40	10.38	8.57	9.49	9.47	9.48
5	Control		10.37	9.38	9.34	9.34	9.61
	Mean over treatments		10.54	9.14	9.55	9.33	
V. Plant height							
1	GA ₃ 60 ppm	85.33	85.73	77.67	75.00	80.93	
2	Mangiferin ppm	60	74.90	74.33	67.00	75.67	72.97
3	GA ₃ 40 ppm		82.07	84.94	77.00	74.67	79.67
4	Mangiferin ppm	40	75.47	65.30	73.67	73.97	72.10
5	Control		79.87	71.22	85.17	72.88	72.28
	Mean over treatments		79.53	76.22	76.10	74.88	
VI. Panicle exertion percentage							
1	GA ₃ 60 ppm	61.60	73.23	67.97	77.23	70.00	
2	Mangiferin ppm	60	62.60	73.90	67.43	70.97	68.72
3	GA ₃ 40 ppm		65.03	74.83	72.60	62.27	68.68
4	Mangiferin ppm	40	63.70	71.10	74.63	65.67	68.68
5	Control		58.70	63.20	66.47	63.17	62.89
	Mean over treatments		62.33	71.25	68.47	67.17	
VII. Grain yield per ha (kg)							
1	GA ₃ 60 ppm	3260	174	189	300	983	
2	Mangiferin ppm	60	2167	238	531	177	778
3	GA ₃ 40 ppm		2300	241	115	149	701
4	Mangiferin ppm	40	2400	100	236	272	752
5	Control		2367	203	223	88	720
	Mean over treatments		2467	191	239	157	

Singh R 2012. Exploitation of heterosis in rice. *Journal of Biotechnology and Crop Science*. **2** (2) : 16-26

Singh Rajesh. 2014. Cultivation of hybrid rice : A complete Package. *Indian Res. Journal of Extension Education*. **14** (2 &3): 6

Singh Rajesh and Lekha Ram. 2012. Ideal hybrid rice seed production package : An Overview Indian Research. *Journal of Extension Education*. Sp Issue. **2** : 244-251.

Singh Rajesh and Sahoo S K. 1997. Artificial and natural

parameters influencing over crossing of cyto-sterile line in rice (*Oryza sativa* L.). (in) Proc. *International Symposium On The Genetics And Exploitation Of Heterosis In Maize And Other Crops*. CIMMYT, MexicoA. **68** : 162-163.

Singh Rajesh and Sahoo S K. 1998. Evaluating hybrid seed production technology along with new growth hormone 'Mangiferin'. *International Rice Res. News*. **23** (1) : 23.

Virmani S S. 1994. *Heterosis and Hybrid Rice Breeding*. Springer Verlag, Berlin. pp. 189.

